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AESTHETIZATION OF THE MODERN AIRPORTS MACRO ENVIRONMENT

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Modern airports are not only complex in terms of functions of the enterprise of transport infrastructure, but also components of urban areas. Given the global trends in the construction and reconstruction of airports, which are becoming urban features, approaches to assess the impact of building architecture on the urban situation and the surrounding environment are changing.

The object of the study is special purpose buildings, namely air traffic control towers (ATC), whose spatial solution and height can significantly change the historical and cultural landscapes, panoramas of cities and urban ensembles.

The visual significance of the latter's architecture is achieved through the use of steel spatial structural systems, with a focus on volumes of basic technological purpose – control rooms located at a considerable height. Individual cultural and historical symbols and components of natural landscapes, stylistic contrasts between ATC building (buildings) and buildings, etc. are actively used.

With the help of light design, they create a kind of light landmarks (beacons) for the movement of passengers, employees and visitors within and outside the airports in the dark and with low visibility in the daylight.

The practice of using ATC buildings for advertising and commercial support of airport operations is being extended. They feature elements of static and dynamic advertising, informational messages; they participate in various light music shows and more. Separate sections of facades, such as stylobate and medium (technical) floors, are used to eliminate the negative impact on the main technological processes.

The negative effects of the construction and operation of high-rise buildings ATC should be attributed to light pollution of the macro environment of airports. To reduce the impact, the restricted areas and size of the display facades, adjusts their mode of operation during the day, etc.

A comprehensive approach to solving technological, urban, architectural, construction, engineering, environmental, and economic problems allows to obtain solutions that provide the unitary purpose of the object with architectural attractiveness (sign) and tolerance to existing and prospective development.